

2nd Tropical Ocean and Marine Sciences International Symposium

TOMSY2020

“Enhancing Tropical Marine and Ocean Knowledge for **Future Sustainability**”

23-24 November

ABSTRACT BOOK

"Ocean of Discoveries for Global Sustainability."

MAKING A LIFETIME POSSIBLE

It is a known fact that human activities have endangered the lives of sea turtles. Without us, they could live a lifetime of 100 years. At MMS, our turtle watch begins with our collaboration with UMT-SEATRU.

We are committed to improve our environmental footprint and embed environmental protection within our business and operational strategy. Join our efforts to protect and conserve sea turtles so that a century of living is possible.

MISC Maritime Services Sdn. Bhd.

A wholly-owned subsidiary of misc
making energy

SEAGRASS ECOSYSTEMS IN CORAL TRIANGLE INITIATIVE CONSORTIUM: STATUS AND THREATS

A.A. Asif¹, M.K. Abu Hena^{2*}, J. Ismail¹, M.H. Idris², N.U. Karim², H.B. Hamli¹, G.J. Gerusu³ and M.K.A Bhuiyan⁴

¹*Department of Animal Science and Fishery, Faculty of Agricultural Science and Forestry, Universiti Putra Malaysia Campus Bintulu Sarawak, 97008 Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia*

²*Faculty of Fisheries and Food Science, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, 21030 Kuala Nerus, Terengganu, Malaysia*

³*Department of Forestry Science, Faculty of Agricultural Science and Forestry, Universiti Putra Malaysia Bintulu Sarawak Campus, Jalan Nyabau 97008, Bintulu, Sarawak, Malaysia*

⁴*Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Marine and Environmental Sciences, University of Cádiz, Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain*

*Corresponding author: a.hena@umt.edu.my

The area of coral triangle comprises 5.7 million km² of the Pacific Ocean with most marine bio-diverse eco-region on planet earth including global hotspot of seagrass species. Many sea creatures of this eco-region are relied on seagrass ecosystem mainly dugong species (total number 2279), sea turtle (4 to 6 species), benthos and fishes. Apart from these ecological services, carbon sequestrations (2.6 billion Mg CO₂ storage) by seagrass ecosystem is also noticeable compared to mangroves and terrestrial vegetative species. This review work scrutinized previously acknowledged seagrass species distributions, species diversity, carbon sequestration, past and present research, and major threats of seagrass ecosystems in this biogeographic region. Depending on different locations six coral triangle initiative countries namely Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Solomon Islands and Timor-Leste have 10 to 19 seagrass species, belongs to four distinct families (Hydrocharitaceae, Cymodoceaceae, Zosteraceae, and Ruppiaceae), which covers almost 58,550.63 km². A total of 21 species of seagrass were found throughout this eco-region, however very few number of research works were conducted to assess the overall status of this eco-regions ecosystems. Seagrass diversity of the coral triangle is also associated with more than 200 million inhabitants, who are being supported directly or indirectly by the resources of this ecosystem. These inhabitants may cause some disturbance to seagrass ecosystems. For long run sustainable management and conservation of these ecosystems, two types of threat are identified which is needed to take into consideration. Local threats are included, water quality deterioration by sewage and pollutant discharge, anthropogenic and agricultural activities, over-exploitation of seagrass associated resources, sediment runoff and destructive fishing. Global threat comprises, sea level rise, macro and micro plastic, global warming, and acidification. Social, cultural, and economic interaction study with seagrass ecosystems and local inhabitants are highly recommended for further study. Globally, seagrass ecosystems and coral triangle initiative area are concerned due to human activities though it contains potentially importance on food services and maintain food web for animals to maintain global ocean ecosystem sustainability.

Keywords: coral triangle; seagrass ecosystems; biodiversity; blue carbon; climate change

